

Education of Exceptional Children in India in the Context of Indian Constitution

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ABSTRACT : Inclusive education forms an integral component of the overall education system and is provided in the mainstream schools committed to an appropriate education for all. It is a flexible and individual support system for children with special needs. In this article, a brief historical development of education for exceptional children, both global and Indian scenario, followed by the development of several acts for education and rehabilitation of physically challenged children in Indian constitution were introduced.

Keywords : Special Education; Inclusive Education; RCI Act; PWD Act; National Trust.

1. Introduction

Special education means specially designed instruction which meets the special educational and related needs of an exceptional child. It is distinguished from regular educational programme meant for non-exceptional children by some unusual quality, something uncommon, noteworthy. It is something special- special materials, special training techniques, special equipments and special help and/or special facilities may be required for special categories of children having special needs. For example, visually impaired children may require reading

materials in large print or Braille. Hearing impaired children may require hearing aid, auditory training, lip reading etc. Orthopedically handicapped children may require wheel chairs, and removal of architectural barriers. Mentally retarded children may need skill training. Related services, such as special transportation, medical and psychological assessment, physical and occupational therapy and counseling may be required if special education is to be effective.

Inclusion means young people and adults with disabilities and/or learning difficulties are being included in the mainstream society. Inclusive

schools help the development of communities where all people are equally valued and have the same opportunities for participation.

2. Special Education to Inclusive Education

Special education is that specifically planned and organized education that is imparted in a special way to all types of exceptional children irrespective of the nature of their exceptionality in proper tune with their well diagnosed special needs for helping them to develop their potentialities and adjust as well as progress in the life as effectively as possible.

The functional definition of special education adopted by us clearly suggests that special education serving the purposes of special children, by its nature itself, must have some uniqueness, specificity and specialty in comparison to the general education available in our schools settings to the vast population of non-exceptional children. But, now question arises, in what aspects does the special education differ from the regular general education provided to the non-exceptional / non-disabled children ? After all, what is special about special children ?

The answer to these and more often likewise questions may be responded well by seeking clarification about the subject considerations, i.e. for whom special education is organized; curriculum considerations, i.e. what type of instructions or learning experiences are to be given through special education; methodology considerations, i.e. how should special education be imparted; placement considerations, i.e. where should the children be placed for receiving special education; human resources considerations, i.e. who is going to impart special

education to the children [Dash 2007, Kar 2007].

Integration is a concept emerged as a philosophy in antithesis of segregation. It is called halt to the system of providing education to the children in segregating settings of special schools and advocated to make provision for their education in the regular schools. In this way, historically, when disabled children were primarily educated in separate special schools, integration was the term carried for describing their successful placement into regular schools.

Inclusion describes much more than the acceptance of children with disabilities / exceptionalities in the mainstream. Inclusive education programmes do not focus on the accommodation of these children into a general education setting, but are focused on the restructuring of schools to accept and provide for the needs of all students. In inclusive education, maintaining and integration are viewed as intermediary steps to the ultimate goal of teaching all students together. In inclusive programme specialized instruction and support are provided to any student who is in need of support without labeling him as disabled or exceptional. In other words, no discrimination is made among the exceptional or non-exceptional children. All the children in all shades of their exceptionality / disability are welcome by making necessary arrangements and accommodations for their education in the same school and classes along with their non disabled peers [Prakash 2008].

For understanding the nature, meaning and concept of inclusive education in a more comprehensive way let us try to make a view of a few well known definitions of the term inclusive education.

According to Michael F. Giangreco (1997), 'Inclusive education is a set of values, principles and practices that seeks more effective and meaningful education for all students, regardless of whether they have exceptionality labels or not' (Giangreco, 1997).

Advani and Chadha (2003) describes, Inclusive education aims to provide a favourable setting for achieving equal opportunity and full participation for all, thus bringing children with special needs well within the purview of mainstream education, it recognizes the diverse needs of the students and ensures equality education to all through appropriate curricula, teaching strategies, support services and partnership with the community and parents. In simple words, it means that all children with or without disabilities learn together.

3. Objectives

Inclusive education is a flexible and individual support system for children with special needs. It forms an integral component of the overall educational system, and is provided in mainstream schools committed to an appropriate education for all. It recognizes and responds to the diversity of children's need and abilities including differences in their ways and pace of learning. It does so by using individualized teaching methods, adapted curricular, as well as tailor made teaching aids and materials.

- I. to enable and empower persons with disability to live as independently and as fully as possible within and as close to the community to which they belong;
- II. to strengthen facilities to provide support to persons with disability to live within their own families;

- III. to extend support to registered organization to provide need based services during the period of crises in the family of persons with disability ;
- IV. to deal with problems of persons with disability who do not have family support;
- V. to promote measures for the care and protraction of persons with disability in the event of death of their parent or guardian;
- VI. to evolve procedure for the appointment of guardians and trustees for persons with disability requiring such protection;
- VII. to facilitate the realization of equal opportunities, protection of right and full participation of persons with disability; and
- VIII. to do any other act which is incidental to the aforesaid object.

4. The International Scenario

4.1. The age of Exclusion : According to Mangal, in ancient civilization the history of treating disability / exceptionality is almost dominated by the philosophy of exclusion, i.e. Totally excluding and exterminating the disabled from the mainstream of the general population through a quite horrified measures like killing, mutilating, burning, excelling, abandoning or making them vanish from the scene some how or the other. The exposure of deformed infants means, taking them outside the settlement to an unknown location and letting them expire in a hole in the ground or drown in a course of water. Exposing them is only way to returning them to the gods. Their births Is the signal of anger of gods.

4.2. The age of acceptance as a subject to Amusement : Many of the disabled children were begin to be utilized as commodities for serving as beggars, prostitutes and slaves. Many families and entertainment establishment like circus companies began to make use of dwarfs and other types of children with deformities and disabilities as an exhibitions subjects or jesters and fools for utilizing the public amusement. In 16th century at Hamburg (Germany) mentally retarded individuals were confined in a tower in the city hall, appropriately named Idiot's Cage. Even in late as in 1815, parents used to take their children for Sunday outing to view the inmates of London's Bethelhem Hospital known as "Bedlom", displayed for public amusement.

4.3. The age of Prohibition : The rise of church as a religious institution in the medieval period led to play a new tone in the treatment and attitude towards disabilities. In collaboration with church, the rulers in the European society established quite discriminatory legal laws deriving the disabled people of their right of inheritance, and forbidding them to testify in a course of justice, making a deed, contract, note or will. The most powerful forces of the days, the rulers and the priests, thus almost made the disabled persons as a subject of crude humour by prohibiting them to play any role in the social life.

4.4. The age of Sympathy : In the second phase of Christian era , disabled children were regarded as those poor souls who have been denied opportunities to lead a normal life on account of the annoyance of the Almighty for committing sins. They were now a subject of sympathy rather than of suspicion or amusement.

The Renaissance Movement in Europe brought the new era of hope to the disabled population.

4.5. The period of Isolated Settings – Special Schools : The spirit of Renaissance gave birth to most of the genuine efforts in the direction if special education for the disabled population. Some of the influencing special education were thus established during the late Renaissance period. The main propagators of this movement like Rousseau, Condillac and Diderot, provided essential theories for the action oriented work of the many pioneers in the field of special education related to various group of disabilities like hearing, visual, mentally retarded. As a result effective procedures in term of providing special education in the segregated settings were devised all over the Europe, USA and Canada for the education and training of the diversified disabled population. As a result by the close of 18th century, special education was accepted as a branch of education and separate schools were established for the education and training of the diversified groups of disabled children all over the Europe including Canada and USA.

4.6. The period of segregated Settings-Special Classes : With the advent of twentieth century, there began a new era in the history of the education for exceptional / disabled in the shape of moving from the isolated settings of special schools to the segregated settings of the special classes within the normal / regular schools. It was the result of a new humanism, coupled with the increasing demands of equality of educational opportunities to all children irrespective of their disabilities in the regular schools run by the Government or funded and supported by the public money. According to Winzer (1993) the movement of disabled

students from institution (special schools) to public school (regular general schools) from isolation to segregation – may be dated from about 1910 with the promotion of permanent segregated classes in public schools. The advent of segregated classes was greeted with enthusiasm, and until the end of 1920s they seemed to meet the needs of these students.

4.7. The period of Inclusive Settings – Regular Classes : The period of inclusive settings i.e. education for all whether exceptional or normal together in the regular classes of the mainstream schools, represents the modern era and latest development in the history of special / disability education. The beginning of this era may be traced as back as 1970s with the evaporation of the optimism surrounding the era of segregated settings of the special classes.

Segregated or special classes for the exceptional / disabled children are responsible for promoting segregation much in the same way as happens in the case of educating them in the special classes.

Children enrolled in the special classes are not able to escape the social stigma. In special classes the children have no role models for learning and advancing including the desired social and other adjustment behaviour needed for living a life in the community settings.

Segregated settings of the special classes perpetuate disability culture and are not helpful in bringing desirable changes in the behaviour of non-disabled children towards their disabled peers.

Internationally the drive towards inclusive education was taken world wide under the leadership of world bodies like UNO and World Bank. Derived from the Universal declaration

of Human Rights (1949) and the UN convention on the rights of the child (1989) UNESCO claimed that being included within mainstream education is a basic human right.

The World Conference on Education for All (EFA) held at Jomtien, Thailand, in March 1990, arrived on the fundamental principle that all should have the opportunity to learn. Children and adults with disabilities do have the right to education, and have the right to be part of the mainstream education system.

The World Conference on special needs education organized by the Government of Spain in cooperation with UNESCO held in Salamanca in June 1994 adopted a framework for action on special needs education by clearing declaring that “education policies at all levels from the national to the local, should stipulate that a child with disability should attend the neighbourhood school, that is the school that would be attended if the child did not have a disability.”

Further International Work by both World Bank and Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has shown that it is far more expensive to operate dual systems of ordinary and special education than it is to operate a single inclusive system. The right of students with disabilities to be educated in their local mainstream school is becoming more and more accepted in most countries and many reforms are being put in place to achieve this goal. Further, there is no reason to segregate disabled students in public education system. Instead, education systems need to be reconsidered to meet the needs of all students.

5. The Indian Scenario

5.1. Pre-Independence Period : In the Vedic Era ‘ASHTAVAKRA’ (a chronic and

severe case of orthopaedic impairment becoming a great scholar by virtue of the educational facilities available to all irrespective of their abilities or disabilities.

The great Rishis (the sacred persons) as Gurus (teachers) were known to provide equal treatment to their pupils irrespective of their social status and exceptional or non-exceptional abilities. They were of the firm believes in the theory of Karma. Therefore they were of the opinion to give ample opportunities to the disabled, poor and sufferers to learn the art of self actualization and doing good in the life for getting better result in the next cycle of life. Consequently the treatment, care and education of the disabled children in India, also passed through the phases or era of exclusion, extermination and abduction, ridicule and amusement, witchcraft, sympathy and asylum. There are instances of the disabled people being harassed, ridiculed and made a subject of amusement and entertainment. The disabled and poor people were treated as subject of sympathy and asylum. In advocating human treatment to disabled Lord Buddha and Mahavira propagators of the doctrines of Buddha and Jaina religions, plays a major role. The rulers like Ashoka the great, Harsh Bardhan, who followed their preaching were earned much fame in establishing hospitals, and asylum for the disabled and destitute [Mangal, (2007);].

The traditional of state funding and also the charitable flow for the care and protection of the disabled continued through the medieval India during the regimes of many Muslim rulers including Mughals. There is no evidence of any type of special provision for the disabled children

during the eras of Indian history prior to the establishment of British rule in the country.

The first school meant for the special education of the deaf was established in Bombay in 1883. In 1887 the first school for the blind was started at Amritsar. The first school for blind and deaf was started at Mysore in 1901. In 1906, the first Government school "The Emerson Institute for the Blind" was started at Lahore. Although the facilities in the form of psycho-medical treatment were available at Ranchi from 1934, yet the first home for the mentally retarded came up at Bombay in 1941.

In real sense under the colonial rule, India had a very marginal and insignificant provision for the education of children including the disabled. When India got independence in 1947, we had only 34 institutions for deaf, 32 for the blind and 3 for the mentally retarded.

5.2. Post- Independence Period : In its constitution, India laid down special provisions through the article 45 stating that "free, compulsory and universal primary education should be provided to all children up to 14 years of age." But the first Education Commission was formed in 1964 namely Kothari Commission (1964-66) set for advising the Government on "the national pattern of education and on the general principles and policies for the development of education at all stages and in all aspects" clearly emphasized that "the constitutional directive on compulsory education to all children, includes handicapped children as well. However, very little has been done in the field so far." Since there were 115 schools for the blind, 70 schools for the deaf 25 schools for the orthopedic handicapped and 27 for the

mentally retarded in the whole country, Education Commission felt that the existing facilities were quite in shortage and therefore suggested to experiment with integration and mainstreaming of disabled students with the non-disabled students in the ordinary schools.

Education Commission, Government of India recommended in its first National Education Policy 1968 that “Education facilities for the physically and mentally handicapped children should be expanded and attempts should be made to develop integrated programmes enabling the handicapped children to study in regular schools.”

In an attempt for implementation of the National Policy on Education, 1968, the Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme was launched in December 1974 under the erstwhile department of social welfare for admitting children with disabilities in regular schools.

6. Act on Rehabilitation of Exceptional Children in India Since Independence

6.1. Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) Act, 1992 :

The Government of India set up Rehabilitation Council, as a registered society under the Societies Registration Act, 1860. Thereafter, this was converted to a statutory body under the Rehabilitation Council of India Act, 1992. The Rehabilitation Council of India is a statutory body under MoSJ&E set up with the twin responsibilities of standardizing and regulating the training of personnel and professionals in the field of rehabilitation and social education. The RCI Act was subsequently amended in 2000, to establish a statutory

mechanism for monitoring and standardizing courses for the training of professionals required in the field of special education and rehabilitation of persons with disability. Training of special educators and resource teachers that can offer support services to children with special needs in regular schools is the responsibility of RCI.

6.2. Persons With Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Right & Full Participation) Act, 1995 :

A landmark legislation in the history of special education in India is the Persons With Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Right & Full Participation) Act, 1995. This comprehensive Act covers seven disabilities, namely blindness, low vision, hearing impaired, loco-motor impaired, mental retardation, leprosy cured and metal illness. Chapter V (Section 26) of the Act which deals with education, mentions that the appropriate Governments and the local authorities shall -

- a. ensure that every child with a disability has access to free education in an appropriate environment till he attains the age of eighteen years;
- b. endeavour to promote the integration of students with disabilities in the normal schools;
- c. promote setting up of special schools in Government and private sector for those in need of special education, in such a manner that children with disabilities living in any part of the country have access to such schools;
- d. endeavour to equip the special schools for children with disabilities with vocational training facilities.

6.3. National Trust for Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation and Multiple Disabilities Act, 1999 :

Another landmark legislation is the National Trust Act, 1999. This Act seeks to protect and promote the rights of persons who, within the disability sector, have been even more marginalized than others. Though the National Trust Act of 1999 does not directly deal with the education of children with special needs, one of its thrust areas is to promote programmes, which foster inclusion and independence by creating barrier-free environment, developing functional skills of the disabled and promoting self-help groups.

The object of the National Trust is to empower families to retain their disabled members within the family and the community. The Trust reaches out to disabled persons and their families and provides a range of relief and care services. Such services may be provided through institutional care or in the homes in case the families and their disabled members are unable to access the services outside the house.

7. Education for Persons with Disabilities

A. Education is the most effective vehicle of social and economic empowerment. In keeping with the spirit of the Article 21A of the Constitution guaranteeing education as a fundamental right and Section 26 of the Persons with Disabilities Act, 1995, free and compulsory education has to be provided to all children with disabilities up to the minimum age of 18 years. According to the Census, 2001, fifty-one percent persons with disabilities are illiterate. This is a very large percentage. There is a need for

mainstreaming of the persons with disabilities in the general education system through Inclusive education.

- B. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) launched by the Government has the goal of eight years of elementary schooling for all children including children with disabilities in the age group of 6-14 years by 2010. Children with disabilities in the age group of 15-18 years are provided free education under Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) Scheme.
- C. Under SSA, a continuum of educational options, learning aids and tools, mobility assistance, support services etc. are being made available to students with disabilities. This includes education through an open learning system and open schools, alternative schooling, distance education, special schools, wherever necessary home based education, itinerant teacher model, remedial teaching, part time classes, Community Based Rehabilitation (CBR) and vocational education.
- D. IEDC Scheme implemented through the State Governments, Autonomous Bodies and Voluntary Organizations provides hundred percent financial assistance for various facilities like special teachers, books and stationery, uniform, transport, readers allowance for the visually handicapped, hostel allowance, equipment cost, removal/modification of architectural barriers, financial assistance for purchase/production of instructional material, training of general teachers and equipment for resource rooms.
- E. There will be concerted effort on the part of the Government to improve identification

of children with disabilities through regular surveys, their enrollment in appropriate schools and their continuation till they successfully complete their education. The Government will endeavor to provide right kind of learning material and books to the children with disabilities, suitably trained and sensitized teachers and schools which are accessible and disabled friendly.

- F. Government of India is providing scholarships to students with disabilities for pursuing studies at post school level. Government will continue to support the scholarships and expand its coverage.
- G. Facilities for technical and vocational education designed to inculcate and bolster skill development suited to various types of productive activities by adaptation of the existing institutes or accelerated setting up of institutes in un-served/underserved areas will be encouraged. NGOs will also be encouraged to provide vocational training.
- H. Persons with disabilities will be provided access to the Universities, technical institutions and other institutions of higher learning to pursue higher and professional courses.

8. Initiatives Taken in India

- A. The Constitution of India ensures equality, freedom, justice and dignity of all individuals and implicitly mandates an inclusive society for all including persons with disabilities. In the recent years, there have been vast and positive changes in the perception of the society towards persons with disabilities. It has been realized that a majority of persons with disabilities can lead a better quality of life if they have equal opportunities and effective access to rehabilitation measures.
- B. According to the Census 2001, there are 2.19 crore persons with disabilities in India who constitute 2.13 percent of the total population. This includes persons with visual, hearing, speech, locomotor and mental disabilities. Seventy five per cent of persons with disabilities live in rural areas, 49 per cent of disabled population is literate and only 34 per cent are employed. The earlier emphasis on medical rehabilitation has now been replaced by an emphasis on social rehabilitation. There has been an increasing recognition of abilities of persons with disabilities and emphasis on mainstreaming them in the society based on their capabilities. The Government of India has enacted three legislations for persons with disabilities viz. (i) Persons with Disability (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995, which provides for education, employment, creation of barrier free environment, social security, etc. (ii) National Trust for Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation and Multiple Disability Act, 1999 has provisions for legal guardianship of the four categories and creation of enabling environment for as much independent living as possible. (iii) Rehabilitation Council of India Act, 1992 deals with the development of manpower for providing rehabilitation services.
- C. In addition to the legal framework, extensive infrastructure has been developed. The following seven national Institutes are working for development of manpower in different areas, namely:
 - Institute for the Physically Handicapped, New Delhi.

- National Institute of Visually Handicapped, Dehradun
 - National Institute for Orthopaedically Handicapped, Kolkata
 - National Institute for Mentally Handicapped, Secunderabad.
 - National Institute for Hearing Handicapped, Mumbai
 - National Institute of Rehabilitation Training & Research, Cuttack.
 - National Institute for Empowerment of Persons with Multiple Disabilities, Chennai.
- D. There are five Composite Rehabilitation Centres, four Regional Rehabilitation Centres and 120 District Disability Rehabilitation Centres (DDRCs) providing various kinds of rehabilitation services to persons with disabilities. There are also several national institutions under the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare working in the field of rehabilitation, like National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences, Bangalore; All India Institute of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Mumbai; All India Institute of Speech and Hearing, Mysore; Central Institute of Psychiatry, Ranchi, etc. In addition, certain State Government institutions also provide rehabilitation services. Besides, 250 private institutions conduct training courses for rehabilitation professionals.
- E. National Handicapped and Finance Development Corporation (NHFDC) has been providing loans on concessional terms for undertaking self-employment ventures by the persons with disabilities through State Channelizing Agencies.
- F. Panchayati Raj Institutions at Village level, Intermediary level and District level have been entrusted with the welfare of persons with disabilities.
- G. India is a signatory to the Declaration on the Full Participation and Equality of People with Disabilities in the Asia Pacific Region. India is also a signatory to the Biwako Millennium Framework for action towards an inclusive, barrier free and rights based society. India is currently participating in the negotiations on the UN Convention on Protection and promotion of the Rights and Dignity of Persons with Disabilities

9. Conclusions

The objective should be to integrate the physically and mentally handicapped with the general community as equal partners, to prepare them for normal growth and to enable them to face life with courage and confidence. The following measures will be taken in this regard:

- i) Wherever it is feasible, the education of children with motor handicaps and other mild handicaps will be common with that of others.
- ii) Special schools with hostels will be provided, as far as possible at district headquarters, for the severely handicapped children.
- iii) Adequate arrangements will be made to give vocational training to the disabled.
- iv) Teachers training programmes will be reoriented, in particular for teachers of primary classes, to deal with the special difficulties of the handicapped children; and

- v) Voluntary effort for the education of the disabled will be encouraged in every possible manner.

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